

CHIZIQSIZ CHEGARAVIY SHARTLAR BILAN PARABOLIK TENGLAMALAR SISTEMASI UCHUN AVTOMODEL YECHIMLAR

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada chiziqsiz chegaraviy shartlar bilan bog'langan parabolik tenglamalar sistemasini hisoblashlarni amalga oshirib, avtomodel tenglamalar sistemasiga keltirilgan. Masalaning kompakt yurituvchili yechimi uchun asimptotika topilgan. Topilgan asimptotik formulalardan berilgan masalani sonli yechishda boshlang'ich yaqinlashish sifatida foydalanilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Nochiziqli tenglamalar sistemasi, reaksiya-diffuziya, global yechim.

Annotation. In this article, a system of parabolic equations with nonlinear boundary conditions is investigated, and it is reduced to a system of self-similar (automodel) equations. The asymptotic behavior of the solution with a compact support is obtained. The derived asymptotic formulas are used as an initial approximation for the numerical solution of the given problem.

Key words: System of nonlinear equations, reaksiya-diffuziya, global solution

KIRISH.

Maqolada quyidagi nochiziqli parabolik tipdagi tenglamalar sistemasi:

$$u_{it} = \left(u_{ix}^{m_i} |^{p_i} \left(u_i^{m_i} \right)_x \right), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k, \quad x > 0, \quad 0 < t < T, \quad (1)$$

nochiziqli chegaraviy shart

$$-1 u_{ix}^{m_i} |^{p_i} \left(u_i^{m_i} \right)_x (x, t) = \prod_{j=1}^k u_j^{q_{ij}}(0, t), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k, \quad 0 < t < T, \quad (2)$$

hamda boshlang'ich shartlar bilan berilgan

$$u_i(x, 0) = u_{i0}(x), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k, \quad x > 0, \quad (3)$$

(1)-(3) masalaning avtomodel yechimlari asimptotikasi va sonli yechimlarini tadqiq etamiz. Bu yerda $k \geq 1$, $p_i > 1 + 1/m_i$, $m_i \geq 1$, $q_{ij} > 0$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) va $u_{i0}(i = 1, 2, \dots, k)$ funksiyalar R_+ da manfiy bo'lmagan uzluksiz funksiyalar.

(1) parabolik tipdagi nochiziqli tenglamalar sistemasi chiziqli bo'lmagan issiqlik o'tkazish, diffuziya, filtratsiya, kimyoviy reaksiya va portlovchi jarayonlarni tavsiflovchi umumiy matematik modeldir hamda tabiatda uchraydigan qator jarayonlarni matematik modellashtirishda keng tatbiq etiladi [1-10].

TADQIQOT METODOLOGIYASI

Avtomodel tenglamalar sistemasini qurishda (1) -(3) tenglamalar sistemasi yechimini quyidagicha qidiramiz:

$$\bar{u}_i(x, t) = (\tau + t)^{-k_i} F_i(\xi_i), \quad \xi_i = x(\tau + t)^{-l_i}, \quad (4)$$

bu yerda $k_i + 1 = (k_i m_i + l_i)(p_i + 1) + l_i$, $(k_i m_i + 1)(p_i + 1) = \sum_{j=1}^k k_j q_{ij}$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$).

Hisoblashlar olib borish natijasida (1)-(3) masala quyidagi ko‘rinishga keltiramiz:

$$\begin{cases} \left(\left| (F_i^{m_i}) \right|^{p_i} (F_i^{m_i})' \right)' (\xi_i) + k_i F_i (\xi_i) + l_i \xi_i F_i' (\xi_i) = 0 \\ - \left| (F_i^{m_i}) \right|^{p_i} (F_i^{m_i})' (0) = \prod_{j=1}^k F_j^{q_{ij}} (0), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

(5) masalani avtomodel yechimni quyidagicha $\bar{F}_i(\xi_i) = (a_i - b_i \xi_i^{\gamma_1})_+^{\gamma_2}$ qidiramiz va uni (5) masalaga qo‘yib hisoblashlarni amalga oshirib, avtomodel yechimga kelamiz:

$$\bar{F}_i(\xi_i) = \left(a_i - b_i \xi_i^{\frac{p_i+2}{p_i+1}} \right)_+^{\frac{p_i+1}{m_i(p_i+1)-1}},$$

bu yerda $a_i > 0$, $b_i = \frac{m_i(p_i+1)-1}{(p_i+2)m_i} k_i^{\frac{1}{p_i+1}} > 0$, $y_+ = \max(0, y)$.

NATIJALAR.

Teorema. (5) masalaning kompakt yurituvchili yechimi uchun $\xi_i \rightarrow \left(\frac{a_i}{b_i} \right)^{\frac{p_i+1}{p_i+2}}$ da quyidagi asimptotika o‘rinli bo‘ladi

$$F_i(\xi_i) = \bar{F}_i(1 + o(1)). \quad (6)$$

Xulosa

Chiziqsiz differensial tenglamalar sistemalarini sonli yechishda eng asosiy muammolardan biri iteratsiya jarayonining barqarorligini va tez yaqinlashuvini ta‘minlay oladigan boshlang‘ich yaqinlashishni to‘g‘ri tanlashdir. Tadqiqot davomida ushbu masalani hal etish uchun qurilgan asimptotik ifodalar boshlang‘ich yaqinlashish sifatida qo‘llanildi va ular sonli parametrlar bilan yaxshi moslashishi isbotlandi.

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